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An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
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ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF SPATIO-SEASONAL VARIATION OF CLIMATIC PATTERN ON AIR POLLUTANT CONCENTRATION IN JALINGO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study assessed the concentrations of Nitrogen oxide (NO), Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and Particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in relation to spatial and seasonal variation in ambient air quality in Jalingo Local Government Area. The main goal of the study was to analyze the climatic patterns and assess their effects on air pollution concentrations in the study area. The climatic elements (rainfall, relative humidity, temperature, wind speed, and sunshine hours) were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency, while data on NO, SO₂, and PM_{2.5} were monitored using a Crownco gas monitor. The results indicated that the concentration levels of NO, SO₂, and PM_{2.5} detected varied in space and time. The concentrations were generally high and above the National Ambient Air Quality (NAAQ) permissible limits during traffic peak periods, especially during the evening period and the dry season, respectively. The level of pollutants across all the sampling points also increases with traffic volume, seasonality, and spatial differences. The study established strong statistical evidence that traffic volume, seasonality, and spatial differences influence the pollutants concentrations at all sampling points. The study recommended the development of road networks and the construction of modern roundabouts and bridges in Jalingo Local Government Area to ease traffic flow and reduce the concentration of air pollutants to acceptable limits. The study came to the conclusion that human activities, including traffic congestion, incomplete combustion, open burning and the burning of fossil fuels, contribute to the high concentration of pollutants in the study area and should be taken into account in addition to other factors in order to mitigate their occurrence.*

Keywords: Spatio-Seasonal, Variation, Pollutants and Concentration.

INTRODUCTION

According to Katoto et al. (2021), air pollution is one of the top causes of death worldwide, accounting for seven million fatalities per year. Clean air is also a fundamental need for human life, but air pollution continues to pose a serious danger to both this need and the health of the environment globally (Hassan and Abdullahi, 2012). Currently, urban air quality is a major issue on the environmental health agenda in

many nations. According to international estimates, about a billion people live in metropolitan areas where they are constantly exposed to health risks from air pollutants (Amegah and Agyei-Mensah, 2017). According to Ngele and Onwu (2015), air pollution has been identified as a significant and difficult environmental issue that affects both developed and developing nations worldwide. It has also been linked to higher

rates of sickness and mortality. The degree and rate of development are reflected in the severity of the air pollution issues in the cities (Grutter et al., 2014). The air pollution pattern changes with different locations and times due to changes in climatic and topographical circumstances, which cause the concentration of air pollutants to vary spatially and momentarily.

According to Manucci and Franchini (2017), air pollutants are movable substances that can have a negative impact on people's health, the environment, and indoor and outdoor construction. They have several negative effects on human health, ranging in intensity from small annoyance to major illness to early mortality (Awe et al., 2015). Air pollutants can harm plants and animals, as well as the health of people. According to Parjuli et al. (2016), the release of air pollutants has caused a variety of problems with city air quality, including photochemical haze, acid rain, and reduced visibility. The ongoing increase in traffic is a significant contributor to this, as vehicle exhaust makes up much of the urban particulate matter (Casseo, 2013). For the sake of everyone's health, it is crucial to maintain breathable air (Cohen et al., 2017).

Road traffic is a major source of carbon monoxide (CO), particulate matter (PM), and hydrocarbons (HCs), which are known as incomplete combustion byproducts. Due to fuel impurities, high-temperature combustion processes produce nitrogen oxide (NO₂), sulfur oxide (SO₂), and heavy metals as by-products as well (Guo et al., 2017). Evaporative emissions and secondary air pollutants like ozone (O₃) and peroxyacetyl nitrate (PAN) are examples of non-combustion products (Guo et al., 2017). Road traffic and industrial pollution are the primary anthropogenic causes of pollution in urban areas around the world, and the amount of traffic congestion in a given

region determines how much pollution is emitted over time. As a result, the health effects of pollutant transportation are becoming more and more significant (Katoto et al., 2019).

In Nigeria, pollution from sources associated with vehicular transportation receives less attention than pollution from general industrial sources and pollution from the oil and gas industry (Magbagbeola 2001). Both the amount of pollution from vehicular transportation sources and the number of vehicles owned per person are rising, which is congested Nigeria's urban roads and raising the concentration of pollutants in the air, raising health risks for the populace (Abam and Unachukwu, 2009). Changes in the seasons or time of year have been noted to have an impact on the air quality as they may have an impact on the dispersion of air pollutants by lowering or raising their concentration in the atmosphere. Seasonal variations in ambient temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and wind direction may also affect the concentration of air contaminants (Kim et al. 2015).

As a result, these pollutants may become confined close to the earth's surface since low wind speeds and high relative humidity do not promote quick atmospheric pollutant dispersion. Depending on the elevation of the area, this impact might lead to an increased concentration of air pollutants at a certain site. The atmospheric pollutants in this region of the planet, where there are two distinct seasons, may differ spatially. As highlighted by Bhatia (2003), air pollutants are disseminated more in the dry season than in the rainy season, when the relative humidity is somewhat low, the wind velocity is higher, and the pollutants have a higher tendency to be promptly dispersed.

Numerous studies have shown that the air quality in Nigeria's urban regions is negatively impacted by vehicle emissions. CO, NO_x, SO_x,

and hydrocarbons were estimated by Utang and Peterside (2011), in Port Harcourt, they discovered that the level of hydrocarbons identified in the atmosphere fluctuated across time and space and was higher than local and international standard limits. Onalapo, (2015); Aliyu et al., (2013); Ojo and Awokola, (2012) and Hena, (2014) recently assessed the level of a few selected vehicular air pollutants, such as PM, CO, NO₂, and SO₂, and discovered that the pollutants had exceeded the Federal Government of Nigeria's stipulated threshold. The levels of vehicular-related air pollution from all the studies conducted revealed a rising trend, thus posing a possible health threat to the general public.

Further studies also revealed that pollution from transportation is large and probably has a negative impact on people's health. For instance, a study by Gazali and Kazeem (2013), found that all of the locations tested in Calabar had high PM₁₀ concentrations and that traffic wardens had a high prevalence of health indicators that may be linked to and made worse by exposure to vehicle emissions. In Kano, Nigeria, Okunola et al. (2012), conducted a study and discovered significant levels of transport-related pollution with potentially dangerous health effects. The concentrations of CO, H₂S, NO₂, and SO₂ measured at some sites were above the AQI established by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), particularly during the dry season.

Increased vehicular movement, increased gaseous waste output, and higher population expansion can all be blamed for the high concentration of these pollutants that the investigations detected. Because of the influx of old and used automobiles into the nation as a result of changes in government policy, the concentration of those pollutants has increased over the past few decades in Nigeria (Abam

and Unachukwu, 2009; Baba et al., 2021). Megaritis et al. (2014) also mentioned in their experiments that low wind speed supports the buildup of pollutants, while high wind speed causes contaminants to be diluted. As a result of variations in dispersion and transport, dry deposition, and marine particle production, wind speed can have a significant impact on the number of fine particles.

More specifically, wind direction has been linked to the dispersion of contaminants (Tecer et al., 2008). The distribution of fine particle concentration to its respective sources can be aided by wind speed and direction (Giri et al., 2008). While radiation initiates photochemical reactions with other pollutants, cloudiness promotes the buildup of fine particles (Giri et al., 2008). While stagnant air masses are created during low temperature occurrences, which result in high particle levels, and vice versa (Wu et al., 2013), temperature affects ambient chemical reactions. Despite the fact that this topic has been the subject of numerous studies, Jalingo Local Government Area has seen little to no research of this kind, and the main goal of this study is to analyze the climatic patterns and assess their effects on air pollution concentrations in Jalingo Local Government Area.

METHODOLOGY

THE STUDY AREA

Jalingo Local Government Area is the Taraba State capital, is located in the North-Eastern part of Nigeria with a land area of roughly 195km² with an elevation of 351 meters above sea level, is located between latitudes 08° 43'N and 09° 07'N of the equator and longitudes 10° 50'E and 11° 25'E of the Greenwich meridian as shown in Figure 1. According to Oruonye (2016), Jalingo Local Government Area is bordered to the north by the Ardo-Kola Local

Government Area, to the east by the Yorro Local Government Area, and to the south and west by the Lau Local Government Area. Jalingo Local Government Area is made up of

ten administrative wards (Turaki A, Turaki B, Sintali A, Sintali B, Majidadi, Sarkin Dawaki, Kachalla Sembe, Barade, Kona, and Yelwa) that make up the city's political and administrative structure.

Figure 1: The Study Area
 Source: Geography Department, TSU Jalingo, (2022).

Jalingo Local Government Area has a tropical continental type of climate characterized by well-marked wet and dry seasons. The wet season usually begins around April and ends in October. The dry season begins in November

and ends in March. The dry season is characterized by the prevalence of the northeast trade winds, popularly known as the harmattan wind, which are usually dry and dusty. The dusty and hazy nature of the harmattan period

also contributes to the causes of air pollution that have serious health effects on human health, like respiratory diseases, diarrhea, typhoid, and bronchitis, in the study area. Jalingo has a mean rainfall of about 1,200 mm and an annual mean temperature of about 29°C. Relative humidity ranges from 60–70 percent during the wet season to about 35–45 percent during the dry season (Bwadi et al., 2021).

The temperature is high all year round because of its latitudinal location. The annual mean maximum temperature range is about 34°C–37°C in the study location in 2021. The observed 2021 annual mean maximum temperature departure when compared with the 1991–2020 (long-term) average shows that the temperature is 1.0–1.5°C warmer than normal (Nimet, 2021). The annual mean minimum (nighttime) temperature in 2021 is between 23 and 26°C, which is between 0.2 and 1.4°C warmer than the average of 1991 to 2020 (Nimet, 2021). There is a distinct drop in temperature at the onset of rain due to the effects of cloudiness. The highest temperature is recorded in March and April. The minimum temperature value for the area can be as low as 18.7°C from December to January.

The rainfall distribution pattern shows a decrease from the South to the Northern part. Jalingo Local Government Area has a mean rainfall of about 2000mm in 2021 (NiMet, 2021). The rainfall duration lasted between 90 and 110 days in the study area in 2021, which is above normal when compared with a long-term average between 1991 and 2020 (NiMet, 2021).

The average daily hours of bright sunshine are about 7-8 hours, and the wind speed averages about 76.1 km/hr. The study area has monthly mean sunshine hours of about 220 from January to April, but decreases to a mean value of 207 hours between June and September due

to an increase in cloudiness. The average sunshine hours for a year stand at about 2,750 hours, and evaporation is generally high due to high isolation.

AIR QUALITY SAMPLING PROCEDURE

The data needed for this study were weather and air quality parameters, the weather parameters such as; rainfall, wind speed, temperature, sunshine and relative humidity for the year 2022 was collected from Jalingo NiMet office. The air quality parameters such as; Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), Nitrogen dioxide (NO) and Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}) were measured using Gasman hand-held detector (Crowcon Instruments Ltd., England) which was rented from Ishaya Abdu Consult Services Limited (IACS) Jalingo, and a staff of the IACS was also assigned for the air sampling processes, and it was sampled twice a day (morning and evening). The sampling was carried out for six months: three months for the dry season (February to March 2022) and three months for the wet season (June to August 2022). The sampling was carried out five times a week at each of the four air monitoring sites.

The four sampling sites were Roadblock, Jalingo Main Market Road, Mile Six Market and Labor House Road as the control site. The three mentioned sites were the busiest and congested area in Jalingo LGA which has high population concentration and economic activities going on within them, while the Labor House site was used as the control site for the study as it was characterized by low population and economic activities. The concentration of the air pollutants was determined by switching on the Gasman detector to the specific pollutants and holding it about 2 meters above ground level. The concentration was then recorded from the digital display when the reading stabilized, and

this was done at each of the 4 air quality sampling sites.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was done using inferential and descriptive statistics. The statistical software used for the analysis of data was IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 25), and Microsoft Excel (Version 2010).

- i. **Pearson Correlation Coefficient:** it is used widely in assessing the level of relationship between two variables. In this study it was used to assess the relationship between some selected air pollutants and meteorological variables.
- ii. **Line Graph:** Line Graph was used to determine the relationship between X (independent variable, which is spatial and

season variation) and Y (dependent variable, which is the selected Pollutants).

- iii. **Simple Mean and Standard Deviation:** were employed to analyze the period’s seasonal and spatial variation of the pollutants using the required data obtained from the field at the course of the study.

RESULTS

SEASONAL TRENDS OF WEATHER ELEMENTS IN THE STUDY AREA

The study revealed that rainfall increased steadily from the month of February to the month of August then decreased slightly in September and drastically in October. In the months of December and January, there was no rain. For the time period under consideration, August had the most rainfall (237mm). Thus, August is when Jalingo receives the most rainfall as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Rainfall Trends
Sources: Author’s Fieldwork (2022).

It was also observed that Jalingo Local Government Area has high relative humidity percentage in August. The lowest relative

humidity was recorded in in February at 28%, while August had the highest relative humidity at 81% (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Relative Humidity Trends
Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

A maximum annual mean temperature of 39°C and a minimum annual mean temperature of 26°C were recorded, as shown in Figure 4. Typically, the highest maximum mean temperature values occurred in the months of March and April, while the minimum mean temperature value was recorded in April. The

highest and lowest monthly maximum mean temperatures were measured in February and March at 39°C and August at 28°C, while the highest and lowest minimum mean temperature was recorded in the month of April at 26°C and January at 20°C as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Minimum and Maximum Temperature Trends
Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

It was observed in Figure 5, that the highest wind's speed was 13.8km/hr. and it was recorded in the month of April and subsequently decline to 7.24 km/h in October. Thus, the study

area has the highest wind speed in the month of April, while the month of October records the lowest wind speed.

Figure 5: Wind Speed Trends
Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

As shown in Figure 6, the study area experiences maximum 9.7 hours of sunshine in the month November, with August having the lowest sunshine at 5.8 hours. Furthermore, it is

hypothesized that the interaction of these climatic factors may have a considerable impact on the seasonal and spatial patterns of pollution concentrations in the study area.

Figure 6: Sunshine Hour Trends
Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

SEASONAL TRENDS OF AIR POLLUTION CONCENTRATION IN THE STUDY AREA

With respect to the seasonal trends of air pollution concentration in the study area, it was

observed that the dry season recorded high level of pollution concentrations than the rainy season. The highest level of NO concentration recorded was 9.55ppm, while SO₂ concentration recorded was 6.60ppm both in the month of February, whereas PM_{2.5}

concentration recorded was 15.12ppm in the month of April as shown in Figure 7. This

report agreed with the Gobo et al, (2012), where higher concentrations of air pollutants were obtained in the dry season.

Figure 7: Seasonal Variation of NO, SO₂, CO and PM_{2.5} Concentration
Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

Mean, Minimum, Maximum and Standard Deviation of Pollutants Concentration

As shown in Table 1, the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation summary of

NO, SO₂, and PM_{2.5} values obtained from the sampling sites in the four locations are shown below.

Table 1: Mean, Minimum, Maximum and Standard Deviation of Pollutants Concentration

	Dry Season			Wet Season		
	NO	SO ₂	PM _{2.5}	NO	SO ₂	PM _{2.5}
Mean	8.0367	5.8733	14.1733	5.2030	3.6067	7.1100
Standard Deviation	1.33238	.65737	.97623	1.02007	.99551	2.33390
Minimum	7.04	5.32	13.17	4.19	2.63	4.57
Maximum	9.55	6.60	15.12	6.23	4.62	9.16

Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

The results on mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation of NO, SO₂, and PM_{2.5} data for the dry and wet seasons are presented in Table 1. The results indicates that the mean of NO concentration ranged from 7.04 - 9.55ppm in the dry season and from 4.19 - 6.23ppm in the wet season, whereas the mean concentration of SO₂ ranged from 5.32 - 6.60ppm in the dry season and from 2.63 - 4.62ppm in the wet

season. The mean concentration of PM_{2.5} ranged from 13.17 - 15.12ppm during the dry season and from 4.57 - 9.16ppm during the wet season. This finding is said to be through as Bhatia (2003), stated that air pollutants are disseminated more in the dry season than in the rainy season, when the relative humidity is somewhat low, the wind velocity is higher, and the pollutants have a higher tendency to be promptly dispersed.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SO₂, NO₂, PM_{2.5} AND CLIMATIC ELEMENTS

Table 2: Relationship between NO, SO₂, PM_{2.5} and Climatic Elements

Pollutants	Rainfall	Humidity	Max Temp	Min Temp	Sunshine	Wind Speed
NO	-.940**	-.934**	.905*	.141	.969**	.399
SO ₂	-.964**	-.935**	.956**	.320	.983**	.539
PM _{2.5}	-.921**	-.872*	.962**	.663	.846*	.829*

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Sources: Author's Fieldwork (2022).

The outcome of the bivariate correlation showed the relationships between the climatic factors and the NO, SO₂, and PM_{2.5} concentrations in the study area. Rainfall and relative humidity had a negative, statistically significant relationship with NO (r = -0.940, p = 0.01) and NO (r = -0.934, p = 0.01). This indicates that NO concentrations increase in the area as environmental variables like rainfall and relative humidity in the study area decline. This demonstrates that NO concentrations can be high regardless of the physical environment, with NO correlation to minimum temperature and wind speed showing no discernible link while weather factors like rainfall and relative humidity are sufficient to cause NO concentrations in the studied area.

Rainfall and relative humidity are significantly correlated with SO₂ in a negative way (r = -0.964, p = 0.01) and negatively correlated with

minimum temperature (r = -0.935, p = 0.001). The outcome demonstrates that decreases in relative humidity and rainfall have a detrimental impact on SO₂ concentration by elevating its atmospheric concentration in the studied area.

PM_{2.5} concentration showed a significant negative relationship with rainfall (r = -0.921, p = 0.01) and relative humidity (r = -0.872, p = 0.05). While PM_{2.5} shows no significant relationship with the minimum temperature. Sunshine showed a positive relationship (r = 0.846, p = 0.05), and wind speed showed a positive relationship as well (r = -0.829, p = 0.05). This finding agrees with Kim et al. (2015), that differences in the ambient temperature, relative humidity and wind speed including wind direction could also vary the concentration of atmospheric pollutants over the seasons.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the study, there were spatial and seasonal (wet and dry) variations in the amounts of air contaminants. This finding depends on a number of factors, including the rate of population increase, urbanization, commercial activity, traffic flow,

industrialization, time of year, and season. The high level of pollution concentration in Jalingo can be linked to the town's standing as a large metropolis, which causes worry despite the fact that the quantities of the gases that were identified varied depending on the area. As a result, there has to be a significant awareness campaign regarding the harmful effects of air pollution as well as continued research into the subject's air quality.

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